

ROBUST

CRISIS GOVERNANCE IN TURBULENT TIMES

Hybridity in Robust Crises Governance: Evidence from Nine European Countries and the EU

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Introduction

It has been widely discussed how the present times have been characterized by polycrisis, i.e., frequent, and acute crises that affect a wide range of sectors, spilling across political boundaries, and possibly producing multiple interacting crises (Zeitlin et al., 2019). European governments have been facing successive crises (the 2008-2010 financial crisis, the migration crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine), each necessitating a mobilisation of significant resources to mitigate its wide-ranging impacts. Alongside the consistent occurrence of crises, public administrations have been experiencing increasing turbulence. Turbulence, defined as “situations where events, demands, and support interact and change in highly variable, inconsistent, unexpected or unpredictable ways” (Ansell & Trondal, 2018, p. 1) has become the norm as administrations have to deal with the direct and indirect consequences of all these successive and overlapping events.

Traditional emergency plans and crisis governance structures, however, have been hardly prepared for constant uncertainty and pressure affecting the ability to respond to turbulence. This is well illustrated in the present study by all of the countries with COVID-19, with existing emergency plans referred to as limited at best and constraining in the worst instances. In order to effectively respond to turbulence, several authors have proposed a new governance paradigm – robustness in crisis responses (Ansell et al., 2022). Robustness is “an instance of dynamic conservatism through which a system bounces forward to maintain some of its key functions in new and perhaps more attractive ways” (Ansell et al., 2015, 92), by stressing the need for agile adaptation in the face of turbulence (Ansell et al., 2021; Capano & Woo, 2018; Ferraro et al., 2015; Howlett, 2019; Trondal et al., 2021).

This report argues that agile adaptation for robustness can be achieved by the use of hybrid forms of governance. Uncertainty and time pressure make actors look for new avenues to adapt by rethinking existing or introducing new hybrid governance tools. In the process of adapting to a new context, actors try to implement different underlying logics – from hierarchy to market to networks. Governance hybrids are established when the governance tools with differing underlying logics are combined, which can lead to complementing synergies and/or conflicting dysfunctions (Brandsen and Karre 2011). The level of robustness is, thus, dependent on the ability of public administrations to implement governance hybrids with positive synergies that create the adequate conditions for choosing and implementing different robustness strategies.

Whilst COVID-19 has inspired a surge of research on crisis governance, some using hybridity as a perspective (i.e. see Wong 2021), there are gaps with respect to the adoption and combinatory uses of different governance tools. Existent research has focused on effectiveness of crisis response structures by evaluating the implementation of response measures (for example, see Jugl 2023). Yet we have limited insight into the factors behind the formation of new governance hybrids, their synergies and dysfunctions. By analysing governance hybrids with more depth, both scholars and civil service practitioners will be able to better evaluate those sets of governance tools and recommend new measures, namely:

- Identifying combinations that mitigate the challenges of the existing crisis governance structures.
- Better evaluating crisis governance structures overtime, as dysfunctions can hamper the viability of governance tools for potential crises in the future.

Analyses of governance hybrids tend to remain relatively static, as they look to provide broad generalisations and focus on single ideal types (Tenbenschel 2018). By taking a more dynamic hybridity perspective on the study of crisis governance structures, the report aims to further the understanding on the adaptability of hybrids to form and reform due to changing tensions. By analysing the factors behind hybrids, their synergies and dysfunctions, we can understand how they interact with the environment and with the established structures. This enables policy makers to better analyse crisis governance structures and strengthen their preparedness to deal with both short-term crises and long-term turbulence. Hence, this report delves into the cross-organisational dynamics in crisis governance structures and the factors that affect the formation and functioning of hybrids in order to respond to poly-crises like COVID-19. The report addresses the following research questions:

- What are the enablers and impediments for the formation of hybrids?
- What are the synergies and dysfunctions within hybrids?
- How do hybrid configurations contribute to robustness strategies?

This deliverable is divided into three core sections – the first part provides the overall theoretical framework, by focusing on existent theoretical knowledge about the formation of new governance hybrids and the dynamics of pre-existing ones. The second part highlights different enablers and impediments, synergies and dysfunctions. The third part focuses on the and the linkages between robustness and hybridity. The deliverable uses empirical illustrations of COVID-19, the refugee and the financial crisis from nine European countries. Furthermore, the report refers to empirical illustrations from the EU level for the COVID-19 pandemic. Figure 1 visualises the core parts of the deliverable.

Figure 1: Conceptual approach for the deliverable

The deliverable builds upon the work already conducted within the ROBUST project and forms a basis for the empirical analysis in WP6 together with the work conducted in WP2, WP3 and WP5. The conceptualisation of hybridity and the operationalisation conducted in D4.1 has served as the basis for designing the theoretical framework for this deliverable. The conceptualisation of robustness and robustness strategies relies on the work conducted in D2.1 and D2.2. With D4.2, the project combines existing theoretical insight with empirical evidence, thus transitioning towards an initial analysis of hybridity. The combination of academic work and primary data collected form a basis for conjectures that will be further tested through in-depth analyses conducted in WP6. The findings of this deliverable were used for the designing the case report

form and the interview guide for D6.1 Integrated research protocol for case studies (D6.1 Appendices 3 and 7).

1. Conceptual framework

1.1. Moving towards hybridity in public administration

The turbulence public administrations are facing has forced them to engage in creative problem-solving. Rather than singular, repetitive, or universal responses, we see a plurality of governance approaches. From creating vast top-down temporary structures to reimagining existing structures, processes and resources, public administrations have found numerous ways to tackle challenges created by crises. This has occurred by combining models that on the surface would have previously seemed conflicting or even contradictory. During COVID-19, top-down orders in crisis governance structures operated alongside network venues that included a wide pool of actors, illustrating a compromise between differing logics. This highlights the creativity of public, private and societal actors that used the options available for them to formulate a crisis response, including forming hybrids.

Hybridity is a very prominent term, finding use in a number of fields including biology, linguistics, and cultural studies (Brandsen and Karre 2011). It has also found considerable application within public management literature, with a steady wave of publications since the 1980s and 1990s and a new wave since the new millennium (Koppenjan et al., 2019). Hybridity serves as a tool to describe situations that go beyond ideal types, with an emphasis on configurations between those ideal types (Skelcher and Smith 2015). In public management literature, the concept of hybridity has helped describe a broad number of configurations that can not be explained by one coordination logic (Jessop 2016). This report makes use of the definition by Brandsen and Karre (2011) and combines it with approaches by Meuleman (2019), and Sørensen and Torfing (2019) – by analysing hybridity through the use of multiple ideal types. Hybridity reflects an attempt to find common ground through specific mixtures that combine elements from ideal types with seemingly contradicting or conflicting rationales (Brandsen and Karre 2011). In governance, hybridity reflects a configuration of coordinated decision-making and implementation that results from combinations of different ideal types to achieve the most suitable outcomes (Meuleman 2019; Sørensen and Torfing 2019).

A hybrid can be composed of single and multiple decision-making and implementation venues that rely on instruments from different ideal types. Ideal type typologies provide a lens to analyse crisis response tools and measures, from decision-making to implementation (Tenbenschel 2018; Meuleman 2019). For example, a single policy decision can rely on multiple governance tools from different ideal types (for example see Levi-Faur 2014 for how multiple instruments can be applied within a single policy tool), such as the use of expert committees that include both network and top-down hierarchical logics. Governmental actors can include external actors for decision-making, but they can also limit the inclusion to experts with specific backgrounds. This highlights how a specific measure or venue can simultaneously use tools with differing coordination logics that can over time complement, contradict and conflict with each other.

In public administration, the trichotomy of hierarchy-market-networks remains the most prominent ideal-type typology (Bouckaert, Peters and Verhoest 2010; Meuleman 2019). The use of hierarchy-market-network in governance literature has been developed towards two connected

goals: a) to provide broad generalisations of specific public administration reform trends over the decades (Pollitt and Bouckaert 2011); and b) to provide a language of classification of governance modes (Bouckaert et al. 2010; Tenbensen 2018). This report adopts the latter perspective, as each ideal type is based on an underlying governance logic, which covers a number of tools and instruments that can be introduced, combined with another logic and phased out. The ideal types are highlighted below in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Governance ideal types

<i>Ideal types</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Examples of governance tools</i>
<i>Hierarchy</i>	Relies on legitimate authority, which involves the use of management and structural instruments to establish a more direct and hierarchical control to achieve goals.	<p>Strong adherence to a prescriptive perspective of contingency plans through prescriptive legislation and instructions</p> <p>Formalised positions of authority, i.e. through cabinet members responsible for the crisis response, chief scientist</p> <p>Emergency resource allocation to task forces and committees to issue orders.</p> <p>Use of penalties for punitive purposes.</p> <p>Prioritising specific information sources over others – narrow perspectives from experts</p>
<i>Market</i>	The use of market-based utilizes instruments focused on incentivization towards specific outputs, and measurement of existing actions to foster spontaneous coordination through rationality.	<p>Procurement and contractual relations with private partners for provision of key infrastructure (i.e. ICT solutions, logistics).</p> <p>Inclusion of private partners for maintaining and providing services</p> <p>Use of incentives through subsidies, grants, taxes.</p> <p>Incorporating additional perspectives from pressure – i.e. economic perspectives from interest groups</p>
<i>Network</i>	The use of solidarity focuses on interdependency through process-related instruments that aim to provide the space for interactions, facilitating knowledge and values to improve learning and (joint) decision-making.	<p>Decentralised networks, composing of multiple actors from national, regional, and local level.</p> <p>Use of inclusive arenas for initial pre-crisis planning and implementation post-crisis (workshops, forums, bottom-up hackathons, collaborations</p>

		<p>between volunteers and first level responders).</p> <p>Creating shared motivation and sense of responsibility during pre-crisis training.</p> <p>Calls for solidarity in following decisions. (adherence to national policies on sentiments of belonging and trust)</p> <p>Prioritising more information sources through holistic perspectives – democratisation of expertise</p>
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Each ideal type possesses distinct advantages and weaknesses, making them theoretically suitable for specific pressures and demands. However, the complexity of the environment, interdependencies between tools and their deployment may challenge the optimal fit of one ideal type governance mode. Within crisis contexts, a core dilemma is formed between the need for leadership and hierarchical command on the one hand (Christensen et al., 2016), and the need for collaboration and networks, as the latter provide flexible and adaptive frameworks (e.g., Comfort and Zhang, 2020; Kapucu, 2006; Moynihan 2009; Nohrstedt, 2018) on the other hand. To alleviate the pressures, public administrations form configurations through governance hybrids that attempt to adapt to this dilemma within their own unique environment in terms of the governance capacity and legitimacy (Christensen et al., 2016).

1.2. Configuring and reconfiguring governance hybrids

Governance hybrids are consistently present in administrative structures, as they are used for policymaking and implementation in various policy fields. As the conditions under turbulence shift, so do hybrids too. There is a built-in flexibility for reacting to stronger turbulence (e.g. the use of slack or redundant resources with the increased workload of the personnel), that departures from routine procedures (Boin and Lodge 2016, Teubner 1983). What makes crisis situations unique is that they present an existential threat for the existing hybrid configurations, testing their adaptability to cope with uncertainty and urgency. As a result, crises create visible and critical junctures for reconfigurations. The moment for reconfiguring may vary depending on the characteristics of the crisis. When governance tools are unable to deal with a crisis, actors are directed to conduct a process of reconfiguration – often through a process of *ad hoc* improvisation - in order to handle the newly pressures from the crisis (Boin et al., 2020).

Whilst the ideal types in place may formulate the initial response to crisis, over time they may become insufficient to handle problems (Boin and Lodge 2016; Boin et al., 2021a). Because crises evolve and the existing structures may stop being able to provide an adequate response, actors start deviating away from the initial instruments and going towards governance mixes that address the problems while meeting the expectations of different stakeholders (Duymedijan and Ruling 2010; Jessop 2003). Governance hybrids are, therefore, compromises between actors regarding preferred governance tools, which makes them prone towards failures over time. The choice for new governance hybrids has to consider both the previously established governance

tools, as well as the viability for solving problems from the crisis (Jessop 2003). Due to this, rather than striving towards the most optimal solution, configurations are often designed with what works in a given context (Tenbensen 2018). As the conditions shift, so too does the viability of the hybrid(s), which is dependent on a number of factors, like the availability of different alternatives, the ability to reflect and analyse the chosen alternatives, and dynamics between different tools and measures.

During the process of reconfiguring towards new governance hybrids, actors also engage in a process of selection among alternative options. As the actors reflect on the available choices, they do so while being subjected to specific biases that may privilege some alternatives and exclude others (Meuleman 2008). The available alternatives are shaped by a number of administrative features. Previous studies have highlighted the role of system level determinants, including structural and cultural characteristics to organisational level factors, including competencies and biases (Ansell et al., 2010; Christensen et al., 2016; Eckhard et al., 2021; Pollitt and Bouckaert 2011; Jessop 2003). This deliverable focuses on process and structure determinants involving the administrative structure (covered in the framework through horizontal and vertical specialisation), organisational competencies (covered in the framework through analytical and self-reflective abilities) and legacies (covered in the framework through past public management reforms) (Pollitt and Bouckaert 2011; Jugl 2023; Bouckaert et al., 2010; Jessop 2003). These characteristics determine the context within which stakeholders operate and therefore affect the available options. The report highlights three specific factors – previous management reforms, specialisation of the administrative structure, and the presence of self-reflective and analytical abilities. The hybrid formation and dynamics within formed hybrids is highlighted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Hybrid formation and dynamics within formed hybrids

First, different administrative structures have gone through previous public management reforms – namely the professionalization reforms in Weberian bureaucracy, the rational behaviour and performance logics of the New Public Management (NPM) or the use of collaborative networks and partnerships with New Public Governance (NPG) (Pollitt and Bouckaert 2011; Meuleman 2019). Whilst each reform wave is a critical response to previous paradigms and has distinct values, in practice each wave is based on combinations and layering with the previous paradigms, establishing new hybrids. In different administrative structures, the bias towards one legacy over another shapes the results, as institutions are path dependent. This affects the built-in flexibility within the institutions themselves, simultaneously enabling and constraining the choice of alternatives (Teubner 1983).

Second, the overall administrative structure and specialisation also plays a role in shaping the potential and direction of new governance hybrids, distinct venues, stakeholder roles and policy measures. Specialisation refers to the dispersion of policy management, with processes, responsibilities and competencies being divided across organisations (Jenkins and Henry 2016). Through specialisation, public officials develop a variety of skills, which can also be applied in crisis situations (Boin et al., 2016). Structures with less dispersion may lean towards more hierarchy-based approaches, whereas specialised structures may rely on networked approaches due to established complex coordination structures for policy-making and implementation. The openness towards the adoption for new alternatives and available resources may also be determinant for new governance hybrids (Tenbenschel 2018). This openness depends on different factors, from past reform experiences to the characteristics of the crisis at hand. Actors experience pressure and urgency, which affect the value priorities that enable and limit the choice of alternatives.

Third, hybridity formation depends on the ability of actors to conduct a process of self-analysis and implement the lessons which follows from it. This process can provide actors substantive (i.e. the impact of school closures on teaching quality) and institutional insights (i.e. best practices in cross-organisational Covid-19 working groups). The learning and adaptation process takes into consideration both immediate feedback as well as previous comparative experiences (Jugl 2023). Such feedback may come from a variety of sources, such as endogenous forms that incorporate the experiences of the individual, organization, or system over the current or comparable crises to exogenous that focus on external experiences of others (Feitelson et al., 2022). The lessons can be obtained from previous crises, but ongoing crises can also provide important lessons. For example, systems that experience turbulence the earliest can provide inspiration and lessons for others (Jugl 2023). The learning process itself occurs through structures, cultures and interactions that determine the receptiveness towards information, the ability to reflect on potential shifts and adjust accordingly (Rashman et al., 2009). This is further altered in crisis settings, where actors are under pressure to short-circuit established processes, but who are also provided with opportunities for sharing broader perspectives and engaging with additional resources in new venues (Lee et al., 2020).

After the governance hybrid has been formed, the configuration is affected by internal dynamics shaping the ability to effectively respond to the crisis and to reform when needed. Governance hybrids consist of governance tools, which interact with each other resulting in non-zero sum games. The non-zero games can manifest through positive synergies or negative dysfunctions. The synergies are exhibited, when the governance tools from different ideal types interact with each other in positive dynamics through capitalising on the advantages or mitigating the disadvantages (Meuleman 2019). The dysfunctions are exhibited in governance hybrids, when the governance tools interact with each other in negative dynamics by conflicting with each other to undermine any advantages or creating tensions by amplifying disadvantages (Howlett and Ramesh 2014). Governance hybrids can vary in permanency, with synergies and dysfunctions affecting its ability to match the crisis environment. Once tensions within governance hybrids have peaked, hybrids enter into a process of reconfiguration, where new combinations are formed (Tenbenschel 2018; Jessop 2003). The synergies and dysfunctions can also affect the reconfiguration process, with actor experiences affecting the evaluation of governance tools.

2. Methodological approach

The report relies on insights from empirical evidence on governance hybridity from nine European countries (Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway and Spain) and from the EU. This was complemented by secondary data drawn from public administration and crisis management literature. The report is based on a variety of examples of hybridization in responses to three crises – COVID-19, refugee, financial. The priority of the data collection was the COVID-19 pandemic, which posed a similar existential threat to all of the partner countries, enabling us to analyse variations in different administrative systems. Furthermore, the transboundary nature of the pandemic involved crisis governance structures with both high and low levels of preparedness. Although the refugee and the financial crisis required adjustments from all administrative systems, the level of turbulence varied more, with, for example, Norway experiencing a limited impact from the financial crisis, Estonia experiencing limited influx of refugees. This variation in impacts limited the ability to study the presence of hybridity in such cases. Furthermore, the recent occurrence of COVID-19 provided more opportunities for primary data collection, including interviews, with stakeholders reflecting on the recent experience of the crisis. This enables deeper insights towards cross-organisational dynamics, which are more difficult to capture with the refugee and the financial crises, because of limitations regarding institutional memory amongst both practitioners and scholars.

The data collection process was coordinated amongst the leads of WP3-5 through a joint 22-page data gathering template, which was developed in collaboration with all the partners to incorporate the flexibility for the idiosyncrasies of national contexts. The development of the template built on the conceptualisation of both dependent and independent variables of the ROBUST project outlined in D2.1, D3.1, D4.1 and D5.1. The template consisted of three core parts across the three crises under study:

- 1) Information on the crisis and response (pre-crisis preparedness, turbulence during crisis, crisis responses);
- 2) Information on the dependent variable (innovativeness and adaptiveness);
- 3) Information on the independent variables (MLG, hybridity, societal intelligence).

All ROBUST partners prepared thorough national reports based on the data gathering template. National reports included information regarding the substantive aspects in primary and secondary responses, as well as the crisis governance structures in decision-making and implementation venues. The reports passed two rounds of revisions from the leads of WP3-5 to ensure the quality of the data. For gathering the relevant country-specific scholarly work, all partners contributed in gathering the prominent academic papers about the three crises, policy responses and their impacts. This was done through searches in the major available search engines (i.e. Scopus, WoS, Google Scholar), as well as consulting with fellow scholars within the academic networks. The scholarly work was complemented through secondary data on the relevant documents. This included the study of national level legal documents (laws and secondary legislation), policy documents, action plans and strategies for crises, websites and other grey literature.

For the analysis of the COVID-19 crisis, the template included a national level analysis, as well as a more detailed focus through two mini-cases per partner countries. The selection of the mini-cases was connected with the policy measures that were common amongst the countries during peak waves and reflected the ability of governments to adjust to meet the new challenges (Boin et al., 2021), i.e., (a) school closures, and (b) vaccination promotion and admission. These measures remained prominent (albeit in varying forms) during the successive waves of COVID-

19 between 2020 and 2022. The selection criteria for the mini-cases also included robustness, which was based on the conceptualisation and operationalisation work conducted in D2.1. The primary emphasis for the mini-cases were venues of policy-making and implementation, where actors met and interacted using different governance tools and measures.

In order to ensure that all three independent variables were covered through primary data collection, the data gathering template also included a joint interview questionnaire with relevant guidelines for conducting the interviews. The joint interview questionnaire included relevant background information on key concepts, guidelines towards the choice of interviewees and strategies for conducting the interviews. The data gathering template also involved self-evaluating analytical questions for researcher to check the quality of data collected. The joint interview questionnaire itself involved broader questions on the independent variables, with optional follow-up questions as potential probes. The interview questionnaire was divided into three broader themes:

- 1) Understanding the crisis response, its implementation, and its societal impact;
- 2) Reflecting on drivers and barriers for adaptation and innovation during crises;
- 3) Understanding the particular experiences and challenges of different actors.

Whilst themes 1 and 3 were relevant for mapping the necessary background information regarding the crisis governance structures as well as actor-centric perspectives, theme 2 was focused on the independent variables (including hybridity). The main question explored the presence of different governance hybrids. This was complemented by follow-up questions regarding the positive and negative dynamics within implemented governance hybrids and the impact of different governance hybrids towards adaptation and innovation. Due to the broad scope of hybridity, the questions were focused mainly on governance hybridity, which was studied through policy implementation.

Altogether 19 mini-cases in school closures and vaccination promotion and admissions were prepared, for which 108 interviews were conducted. The interviews were conducted following the ethical principles of D1.1 Project Handbook. This also determined the approach for the selection of interviewees, with both gender balance as well as vulnerability of individuals kept in mind. The interviewees were selected based on their roles, with the aim to cover the perspectives of the different types of stakeholders. Interviewees included:

- representatives of national, regional and local public sector decisionmakers;
- public health agency manager; politicians/administrators in central government;
- civil society organization staff;
- experts and task force members;
- journalists having covered the relevant mini-case.

The broad range of interviewees provided a more comprehensive picture of the empirical examples, which enabled a better understanding of the linkages between the relevant factors. The mini-cases varied from local to regional to national level, which helped to better grasp the relevant factors in different levels in both horizontal and vertical interactions. The depth of the mini-cases provided a basis for further theoretical conjectures regarding formation of governance hybrids, its dynamics and linkages to robustness. The overview of mini-cases is provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Mini-cases

Country	Vaccination mini-cases	School closure mini-cases
Belgium	Vaccination promotion in the Flemish region	School closures in the Flemish region
Czechia	Large scale vaccination centre in Brno	School closures in Czechia
Denmark	Vaccination prioritization and promotion in Ishøj Municipality. Covid response Crisis Unit in Nord-Funen Municipality	School closures in Denmark
Estonia	Vaccination prioritisation and admission	School closures in the City of Tallinn
Hungary	Vaccination promotion in Hungary – case of the “Immunity card”	Schooling of Hungary’s rural Roma communities during the COVID-19 pandemic. A case study of a village in Eastern Hungary
Italy	The early stages of the organization of the vaccination campaign in Italy	The introduction of special mobile desks in Italian schools in 2020
Netherlands	Vaccine promotion and admission on local markets in vulnerable neighbourhoods in the Netherlands. A tailored vaccine strategy in a Christian orthodox fishing community in the Netherlands	Upholding basic educational functions during COVID-19 induced school closures
Norway	Consolidation of responses at a municipal Covid Centre	-
Spain	Vaccination Prioritization and promotion in the region of Aragón	School closures/reopening In the region of Aragón

Alongside the data collected at the national level, the hybridisation examples on the EU level were also looked for. The data collection focused on measures from different policy fields, gathering primary data from three empirical examples: the Freedom of Movement in the Schengen Area, Vaccine Procurement, and the Recovery and Resilience Facility. The cases include horizontal deliberations across the different EU level institutions (i.e. the European Commission, the European Council, the European Court of Auditors and the European Ombudsman) and the vertical dimension through the Member States’ perspective on the supranational level. For the study of examples of hybridisation on the EU level, the original interview questionnaire in the data gathering template was modified, and 13 additional interviews were conducted.

Data analysis was conducted through a data analysis template, which was developed in collaboration between Tallinn University of Technology and University of Antwerp. The template

systematised and structured the data from the national reports (including the mini-cases) and the EU level case studies. The data analysis template was designed on the basis of the theoretical framework highlighted in section 1 of this report. The approach builds on the operationalisation and conceptualisation of hybridity that was conducted in D4.1. The structuring and the subsequent analysis focused towards three themes:

- 1) Enablers and impediments for the formation of hybrids;
- 2) Synergies and dysfunctions within established hybrids;
- 3) Linkages between hybridity and robustness strategies.

For ensuring the reliability of data analysis, the authors independently tested the template on mini-cases from two country partners (Italy, Denmark) and compared the findings. Following the necessary adjustments, the authors conducted data analysis of the country reports and the mini-cases by focusing on the three themes. The synthesis of the data collected is presented in the subsequent sections of the report. The data collected was utilised to complement existing theoretical insight and explore new potential dynamics or connections between hybridity and robustness. As a result, the analysis didn't elaborate on the relevance or strength of specific factors, but rather provided an explorative overview of the potential factors. These linkages will be further studied in WP6, which conducts an in-depth empirical analysis.

3. Theoretical and empirical findings

3.1. Enablers and impediments in configuring hybrids

Crises require actors to become creative to respond to the pressures experienced. Although crises are similar in the underlying characteristics of pressure and threat towards the administrative system (Wolbers et al., 2021), crises still vary considerably. These variations relate to the duration and transboundary impact (Boin et al., 2021), the preparedness of actors and venues for anticipated risks, and the relation to the primary activities (Berthod et al., 2017). Based on crisis characteristics, public administrations formulate a crisis response, temporarily or permanently changing structures, processes and actors. Through crisis-induced shifts, administrative systems may experience opportune moments, where the lessons learnt lead to both short-term mitigation as well as to capacity building for long-term perspective by addressing persistent problems (Ansell et al., 2022). Crisis governance structures can therefore become more adaptable in moments of crises, as they have more governance tools for shifting available resources and utilising existing capacities in turbulent environments (Boin et al., 2021). However, there are also distinct challenges present for public actors. The urgency and uncertainty, caused by the crisis, puts actors in a difficult position, where they have to include trade-offs with established core values to maintain the core functions of processes (Boin and Lodge 2016). With the context of poly-crises that modern public administrations face, designing and implementing a crisis response becomes a difficult balancing game, as existent governance tools and processes that provide the legitimacy and effectiveness expected by citizens become increasingly difficult to foster and maintain. With the crisis developing and shifting between peak and off-peak moments, the adaptability of crisis governance structures is contingent on the role of positive enablers and negative impediments in affecting the choice of alternatives. As was mentioned in section 1.2, this report covers three distinct elements: **past reforms, specialisation and self-reflective and analytical abilities**. The forming of hybrids is visualised in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Enabling and limiting factors in formation of hybrids

Prior management reforms possess an important role in enabling and impeding available options. As public administrations face new turbulent conditions, the viability of options shift accordingly. The established paradigms can be both enabling and impeding for public managers. The enabling effect of prior reforms was highlighted through both its role in broadening available options as well as in shaping the framing of alternatives. The perceptions on the impact of past reforms can facilitate a more open perspective towards governance tools and measures with varying underlying logics (Baekkeskov 2016, Ansell et al., 2022). The ability to combine governance tools that were introduced through different past reforms, provides actors with more options for designing crisis governance structures.

- During the Covid-19 pandemic, the crisis response unit within the Danish municipality of Nord-Funen provides an example of broadening available alternatives through a comprehensive analysis and experiences from previous reform trends. Rather than relying on a dominant paradigm, either through top-down orders from the executive, incentives through specific benchmarks or relying on the legitimacy from broad inclusiveness, the municipality adopted a contingency-based approach that was underpinned by considerable autonomy from the central government. Namely, the professionals within the municipality were encouraged to self-organise with the choice of governance tools that would be able to customise national level guidelines to the local level. This highlights an overall strategy that strongly encouraged openness of available choices to adapt to different situations.

Alongside expanding the openness towards different governance paradigms, prior reforms can provide relevant experiences enabling additional options during the configuration of hybrids (Baekkeskov 2016).

- During the first peak wave of COVID-19, the schools and the municipalities in Estonia were provided additional options for shifting towards the digital format. Prior reforms (e.g. development of digital platform for study materials, study information systems) had already established strong working ties with developers, who had awareness of the needs and the digital infrastructure of the schools and the Education and Youth Board. This provided actors more options for governance hybrids of hierarchy, market and network, as previous networks provided flexibility for alternative selection.

- During the refugee crisis in Spain, the regional and local governments established the suitable conditions for market and network hybrids to develop. In 2015, several municipalities and regions developed plans (i.e. Refugee Reception Plan in Madrid, Barcelona Refugee City Plan), which created the incentive systems and available resources for scaling up established collaborations with NGO's. Supported through newly established plans, they helped scale up the operations of already established civil society organisations (i.e. Comisión Española de Ayuda al Refugiado, Asociación Comisión Católica Española de Migración, Spanish Red Cross), which offered reception programmes with key services as basic needs, including food, medical assistance and shelter. This was done through subsidising their activities and incentivising existing networks to scale up their activities. This relied on decades of experience from the civil society organisations to mobilise the respective communities with new resources.

However, prior public management reforms can also provide constraints towards the choice of measures to coordinate a crisis response. This can occur through cognitive biases, with previous management reforms instilling biases (both positive and negative) to specific coordinating logics. Furthermore, prior management reforms can lead towards suboptimal crisis governance structures, which possess limited resources for utilising new governance tools. Previous reforms may also be oriented towards goals (i.e. improving efficiency, shifting power balance in administrative structures) that can result in lack of available competency and resources for adopting new options.

- Prior and during COVID-19, in Estonia the audits by the State Chancellor highlighted the limited competencies of public organizations to shift into emergency mode due to lack of crisis planning and the ability to coordinate between actors. This limited the ability of actors to form certain governance hybrids. The choice of governance tools relied on established measures, with a combination of hierarchy and network utilised. The limited awareness led to exclusion of relevant actors, which impeded the choice of alternatives.
- During the refugee crisis in Hungary, the central government opted towards a highly hierarchical strategy in line with the previously established priorities in terms of centralisation of power. Network-based measures remained limited, as the top-down articulated political framing (like refugees posing threats to the national identity) and active discrediting of NGO's on the national level left new grassroots initiatives in the periphery, with local governments engaging in limited collaboration.

Prior reforms can also result in an overreliance on a single dominant logic. Which in turn creates impediments in times of crises by excluding highly relevant information and creating suboptimal communication (Boersma et al., 2019).

- For the crisis response in covid-pandemic, Czechia implemented a top-down control structure. This followed a tradition established by previous reforms of strong state authority for solving different turbulent situations. This resulted in a level of rigidity regarding the establishment and adjustments within planned crisis management teams on the national level. This made it difficult for the crisis teams to expand in terms of the stakeholders and available perspectives, which resulted in some societal actors which perceive them being increasingly excluded from the key decisions.

Another relevant factor influencing the available choice of alternatives is in relation with the **administrative structure and degree of specialisation**. High and low degrees of specialisation both provide potential advantages for forming new hybrids. High horizontal and vertical specialisation can be enabling because of the opportunities for higher plurality of perspectives and customised options (Cristofoli et al., 2022). This can serve as a basis for facilitating a more comprehensive toolbox for the cross-organizational coordination of the topic. This ensures that logics guiding the different processes of the crisis response (from monitoring the spread of the pandemic to deciding on school closures to instituting new teaching methods) are covered during the formulation of the hybrid.

- For the vaccination promotion during COVID-19, Spain attempted to improve the appeal towards different socio-economic groups and established a hierarchy and network hybrid. To gather the relevant perspectives, the region of Aragon and the City of Zaragoza established a number of temporary interaction venues with each other and the different actors (including informing the City of Zaragoza on the measures, meetings with religious leaders, and coordinating vaccination activities with neighbourhood associations). This enabled the use of different coordination logics – from the rapidity and clarity from top-down hierarchical information provision to the legitimacy enhancement and broader perspectives which comes with wider inclusiveness from networks.

However, systems with higher degrees of specialisation can also involve challenges that limit the range of available governance options. Crisis governance structures may experience challenges in responding to pressures from crises, as the relevant competencies may be divided between multiple actors, which result in considerable transaction costs between all actors (Jugl 2023). This can hamper the choice of alternatives, as crisis governance structures are unable to make timely responses to the crisis.

- For example during the COVID-19, the Dutch local municipality Urk implemented very distinct hierarchy and network hybrids. , which had a strong adherence to communal and traditional values, designed and implemented locally often ad hoc crisis response measures that needed to duplicate the work of central crisis response institutions to establish and maintain legitimacy in relation to the very unique local dynamics that were present prior to crisis. This led to very distinct alternatives hierarchy and network hybrids.

Administrative structures that are less dispersed can also include enabling elements facilitating the formation and reconfiguration of hybrids. A more unitary structure can provide more clarity and timely responses, making use of the momentum available from crises (Boin and McConnell 2007). High levels of established legitimacy and perceived importance of the problem provides actors with the opportunity to redesign existing configurations, bringing forth considerable reform to the existing governance structure.

- During COVID-19, Estonia's crisis response structure included an expert group, the Scientific Advisory Board. Whilst the new hybrid and network configuration initially experienced challenges in defining its roles, later on it was perceived as a considerable success, complementing a hierarchy-dominant venue with network perspectives through broader expert-based perspectives and decision-making. The positive perception from actors involved show its potential importance as a key venue for future crisis responses.

This highlights an interesting dynamic, where the momentum provides new pathways for responding to fluctuating turbulence in the long term.

Less dispersed systems may also limit the availability of alternatives, as they engage less stakeholders, thus limiting the ability to analyse and consider these different alternatives (Hermannson 2016). Moreover, in the choice of new governance tools and measures, actors may further possess biases that limit the introduction of other coordinating logics, resulting in vicious cycles.

- In Hungary, whilst the covid crisis governance structure was formed around a collegial body with network-like features with the potential to broaden available perspectives, the venue was nevertheless primarily determined by the existent power balance within the administrative structure (in terms of e.g. information dissemination practices, actor inclusion and chosen communication style). The increased importance of central actors and their lack of willingness to adjust or adapt limited potential learning opportunities.
- Similar dynamics were present in Hungary during the refugee crisis as well. The central government mostly engaged actors and stakeholders (primarily long-term partners within established venues like the Charitable Council), who did not contest the framing and position of the central government, thus limiting new opportunities as well as the analysis of available alternatives.

Linked with previous management reforms and specialisation is the **ability of actors to self-reflect and analyse the availability and viability of different configurations**. This refers to the detection, monitoring and response formulation in crisis situations. It includes the flexibility to shift resources, the analytical skills to analyse the problem and formulate the solution, as well as the ability to include and communicate with relevant actors (Wolbers et al., 2016). Such an ability might enable the search for new alternatives, as actors (public, private and societal) are able to be self-reflexive and creative about the opportunities through changing processes, structures and actors.

- During the covid pandemic, the municipality of Urk in the Netherlands, highlighted the enabling effect of strong reflective abilities. In Urk the national crisis response structure proved ineffective. An alternative hybrid governance configuration, combining hierarchy and network governance modes, was initiated bottom-up by the general practitioners to improve the vaccination take-up rates. The use of national level top-down guidelines adapted towards the local level by the mayor together with the initiative of local stakeholders facilitated a new governance hybrid. The approach adopted by Urk was possible, as actors were willing to adopt new roles, adapt existing ones and establish new coordinating venue(s). The executive health agency possessed the ability to reorganize the procedure for the provision of vaccines and the stakeholders negotiated an alternative approach that was still in adherence to top-down national level guidelines.
- During the refugee crisis, several countries had implemented cross-sectoral collaborations, engaging a variety of policy tools and governing measures using hierarchy, markets and networks. In the case of Belgium, the reception system exhibited considerable resilience in responding to the refugee crisis. For example in the region of Flanders it included actors such as the public agency Fedasil, the local authorities, and non-governmental organisations, Red Cross, Cire and Vluchtelingenwerk Vlaanderen), which were coordinated primarily by public actors on national, regional and local levels

through a mix of hierarchy, network and market governance mechanisms. The ability to reflect and reevaluate existent roles enabled the actors in the network to successfully *ad hoc* activate new private and societal actors and processes (i.e. provide housing for asylum seekers after positive assessment to the asylum request).

The lack of ability of decision-makers to evaluate the availability and the viability of different governance hybrids can limit the potential crisis response. With suboptimal approaches, actors may become fixated towards a set number of options, with potential alternatives being excluded (2019; Baekkeskov 2016; Christensen et al., 2016). This can result in actors having to contribute more resources towards conflicting or duplicating processes, resulting in a gradual participation fatigue of actors and potential options (Boersma et al., 2019).

- A prominent example was highlighted in the case of Covid-19 with the shift towards a digital working format. This constituted a major shift for existing teaching practices and related working processes for schools. For the case of Hungary, the national level guidelines regarding school closure relied on different formats, but primary emphasis was on digital teaching, which relied on available digital infrastructure. Whilst the scheme also involved programmes to build up the relevant infrastructure or provide alternatives, the lack of vertical interactions between the central and local level caused challenges for smaller communities. This was especially difficult for the vulnerable Roma communities, where the available resources and level of infrastructure was low. The lack of vertical coordination between the levels resulted in the local actors opting towards duplicating processes through a network at a local level to guarantee opportunities for education.
- Similar experiences were exhibited for the refugee crisis as well. The reception system in Italy highlighted the challenges in establishing vertical coordination in moments of increased pressure towards the refugee reception system, manifesting in divergence from the intended system. The reception system was split into two separate systems. The permanent ordinary system (SPRAR) with limited capacity to be the primary venue for refugee reception and emergency system (CAS) for increased flows of migration. Whilst the actors within the reception system attempted to expand the SPRAR system through different incentives (informal rule not requiring to establish CAS center, if they joined the reception system), the voluntary nature of it failed to attract local governments to join up, which led refugees being received and accommodated for longer periods through the emergency system CAS than expected.

Configuring governance hybrids is a complex process involving the co-existing dynamics of multiple factors from the wider administrative structure to the self-reflective abilities of individual actors. The enablers can facilitate governance hybrids with a broad range of governance tools and establish synergistic cycles, where the positive feedback from the initial chosen governance tools motivates actors to be more open in the future with regards to other potential alternatives. The impediments can limit the options that governance hybrids have available and also lead to vicious cycles, where actors exclude certain governance tools or actively undermine it after its implementation. The dynamics between the enabling and impeding factors pose a key factor in determining the overall adaptability of governance hybrids to configure and reconfigure. As actors engage in the process of alternative selection, they also engage in choices regarding the short-term mitigation of crises and long-term capacity-building for addressing fluctuating turbulence.

3.2. Empirical findings – Beyond zero-sum games, synergies, and dysfunctions of hybrids

Once the new hybrid governance configurations have been established, governance tools combine resulting potentially in positive synergies and/or negative dysfunctions. The combination of different tools and measures for coordination may provide a positive-sum dynamics, resulting in more positive effects by having governance tools supplement each other (Tenbenschel 2018). The governance tools supplement each other by mitigating the weaknesses or complementing for the advantages present in governance hybrids. However, governance hybrids rarely highlight exclusively positive dynamics, as new configurations enter an already established patchwork of governance tools and measures within complex administrative structures that create different pressures (Eckhard et al., 2021). Task forces, working groups, committees formed *ad hoc* in times of crises may experience challenges from a number of factors – ranging from shortage of resources, over conflicting interests of actors, to lack of trust from citizens – that impede their viability. Governance hybrids can experience internal tension between governance tools which can result in challenges reaching the established goals (Jessop 2003). External tensions may arise in response to the pressures derived from the crisis. The dysfunctions can amplify to the extent that the hybrid becomes unviable and disintegrates. The dynamics are reflected in Figure 4.

Figure 4: The dynamics within formed hybrids

Key elements fostering the viability of governance hybrids are the compatibilities and conflicts between the different ideal type approaches. Governance hybrids sometimes make use of all the ideal types within the hierarchy-market-network trichotomy. Furthermore, ideal types often possess asymmetries, as some governance tools tend to be prioritised over others. The report focuses on the dynamics through bilateral interactions within hierarchy-network, hierarchy-market and market-network hybrids. Analysing synergies and dysfunctions present in the bilateral interactions exemplifies how public administrations are able to develop necessary capacities for responding to crisis pressures. Bilateral interactions shape the internal dynamics of governance hybrids, allowing them to adapt and change when existing tools and configurations are

inadequate for solving problems. These synergies and dysfunctions are illustrated in Table 3. The examples of synergies and dysfunctions highlighted in table 3 are based on the findings from existing academic literature and empirical data collected from country reports.

Table 3: Synergies and dysfunctions of hybrid configurations

Hybrid configurations	Synergies	Dysfunctions	Examples from country reports and mini-cases
Hierarchy and network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circumvent processes for urgency Clarity in roles Access to broader perspectives Input and throughput legitimacy for decision-making process and the decisions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Duplications in processes Confusion in roles Increased fatigue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subnational crisis committees adapting to local contexts National level crisis committees including subnational actors Expert committees role allocation
Hierarchy and market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activate latent resources Encourage further contributions from actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overfocus on established goals Misdiagnosing the problem Limited perspectives hampering legitimacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emergency resources provided for the crisis committee (contractual relations with private and societal actors) Implementing indicators to monitor turbulence Supporting innovation clusters for ideas
Market and network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actors are motivated to contribute beyond initial intentions Fosters openness towards flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges in controlling the deviations within the venues Changes too slow to capture the crisis momentum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private and societal actors exchanging resources based on incentive systems relying on shared responsibility Renumerating long-term volunteerism

In the following subsections (3.2.1.-3.2.3.), the report focuses on the different forms of hybrids in more detail, elaborating on the synergies and dysfunctions.

3.2.1. Hierarchy and network hybrid

The use of command and control embedded in hierarchical governance, combined with solidarity emerging from network governance, has been one of the core tenets within crisis management literature (Moynihan 2008). The combining **dynamics between hierarchy and networks** provide several avenues for positive complementary dynamics, which aim to capitalise on the advantages provided by the ideal types. The hierarchy-dominant top-down orders provide speed and clarity, yet these may be complemented through more inclusive venues for concertation and participation (Boin et al., 2021). Inclusive venues provide access to new perspectives, which can be crucial for comprehending the effect of poly-crises and the impact of solutions (Peters et al., 2022).

- In Czechia, the application of national level guidelines regarding school closures during the Covid pandemic on the local level resulted in the establishment of subnational crisis committees. These committees adopted broad inclusiveness (bringing together public actors in emergency services, social services, private companies as well as societal actors like NGO's and neighbourhood associations) to provide the relevant input for interpreting guidelines in order to adopt them tailor-made to the local level and better understand the consequences.
- The combination of hierarchy and network was also very prominent during the refugee crisis. The refugee reception system in Estonia relied on collaborative ties with the relevant civil society organisations (Estonian Refugee Council, Estonian Human Rights Centre, Johannes Mihkelson Centre). The civil society organisations provided the knowledge on key processes and services in refugee reception to local and national levels for whom the topic had been previously of low importance.

Additionally, the network-based measures can be a crucial instrument for providing necessary input and throughput legitimacy for hierarchies at crucial moments (Hendriks 2022). This not only provides access to more options due to broader perspectives and resources, but also the opportunity to enact more options due to improved legitimacy (Eckhard et al., 2021).

- In Belgium, the National Security Council (NSC), the main crisis management body during the covid crisis, broadened its inclusion rules by extending the membership to representatives of the subnational government alongside members of the federal government to establish legitimacy towards the body.
- The increase in political salience during the refugee crises resulted in similar positive dynamics being exhibited through access to additional perspectives and resources. In the case of the Netherlands, the national level and local municipalities compensated their limited resources through collaborations with CSO's and other volunteer initiatives. Whilst through hierarchy the overall direction was set and venues for coordination mandated, the volunteers and CSO's contributed the relevant perspectives for customising to local contexts. This served to improve the legitimacy of the integration process amongst the local communities by engaging them more actively in the process.

Hierarchy-based instruments also possess a role in the maintenance of positive complementing dynamics. Crises can subject crisis response structures to considerable pressures, which can result in the necessity to prioritize issues and fast-track lagging processes (Meuleman 2019). Hierarchy can help maintain the overall legitimacy of the crisis response by adjusting the urgency in processes.

- In the case of the Nord-Funen municipality in Denmark, the municipality made use of a wide range of coordination approaches based on contingency to react to fluctuating levels of turbulence with COVID-19. The role of the local crisis unit was shifted accordingly. In moments of urgency, the local crisis unit was bypassed through direct implementation of national level guidelines, thus opting for a more hierarchical approach in the mandate of the executive. In more complex issues, the coordination shifted towards a more balanced hierarchy and network hybrid, with the top-down mandate giving the local crisis unit the legitimacy to make decisions.

However, the dynamics between hierarchical control and solidarity can deepen the already existing tensions. The lack of clarity in roles can create duplications or even conflicts between stakeholders, with a shift of roles (Hermannson 2016).

- In the case of Estonia, the COVID-19 crisis response structure resulted in the central government establishing an expert committee (Scientific Advisory Board). However, whilst the use of hierarchy established and formalized the venue, it failed to clarify roles between the actors. This resulted in confusion within the Scientific Advisory Board (its purpose and goals), as well as negative dynamics between the central government and the Scientific Advisory Board (task allocation between the two) and with the wider public.
- The shift of roles was also present in the financial crisis, with countries circumventing suboptimal processes and designing new approaches with the supporting administrative structures. In Hungary, the financial crisis provided an opportunity towards a shift in stakeholder engagement and coordination with the Széll Kálmán Working Group (SKWG). The newly established hierarchy and network hybrid (albeit dominated by hierarchy as it extensively involved both political and administrative/technical elements, while private sector and NGO's were included marginally) shifted the role of actors towards a more top-down approach, thus negatively affecting the perceived quality and legitimacy of the working group.

A reliance on solidarity by market-network hybrids may be hard to sustain over time as actors experience participation fatigue (O'Flynn 2020). The initial motivation to contribute through personal time and resources may reduce as the crisis shifts from peak to off-peak moments.

- In Denmark, the school closures during the peak of COVID-19 resulted in new formats (i.e. outdoor teaching, introducing online systems) to provide children the opportunity for learning, yet following the crises they were mostly discontinued. This was the case despite the positive feedback provided by teachers on the new formats. The overreliance on the internal motivation of teachers to contribute additional time led to unrealistic demands. Furthermore, the national curriculum was not adjusted, which led to relatively low compatibility with outdoor teaching.

From the study of hybrid and network hybrids at the EU level, examples of governance hybrids further highlighted positive synergies and negative dysfunctions. EU level examples showed that adjusting to the urgency of responses and fostering solidarity created positive synergies and broader agreement amongst participants. Regarding positive synergies, maintaining the core values of the supranational level through the Freedom of Movement in the Schengen Area necessitated the use of governance tools from both hierarchy and networks. The dynamics between core values at the supranational level (Schengen area) and the national level (territorial

sovereignty) were under pressure due to the transboundary threats from the covid pandemic. A hierarchical logic was adopted on the supranational level to implement and fast track legislation, exemplified for instance with the implementation of the digital green certificate. In the case of maintaining the Schengen area the priority was reliant on the ability to bring member states together and establish consensus. This coordination was also supported by the underlying coordination framework of the Integrated Political Crisis Response (IPCR), which exhibited elements of network logic.

However, in establishing and maintaining a hierarchy and network governance hybrid, certain dysfunctions also were exhibited by actors. The broadness of inclusion both vertically and horizontally in supranational venues resulted in challenges aligning perspectives of the different actors. Furthermore, the complexity led to challenges in establishing and maintaining interactions between the different institutions and venues. The complexity of the venues also resulted in communication challenges during times of urgency. Although the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) was mandated the responsibility for distributing the knowledge and information during the crisis response, different supranational institutions adopted their own advisory bodies and venues disseminating information. This created confusion about roles and responsibility.

The mixing between networks and hierarchies exhibited a number of dynamics relevant for the operating of governance hybrids – reacting to the urgency present within decision-making, over the inclusiveness of actor composition, to clearly allocating roles and responsibilities. These factors foster the ability within administrative structures to shift and in need to engage in a new process of reconfiguration. The ability of administrative systems to maintain flexibility becomes crucial in times of crises for adjusting the processes, actors and structures to meet fluctuating demands.

3.2.2. Hierarchy and market hybrid

The use of incentives and rational behaviour logic may become crucial within crisis contexts, as actors become in need of resources, necessitating exchanges. The **dynamics of control from hierarchy alongside the incentives of markets** can be crucial in designing new venues for activating latent resources and encouraging further contributions from actors (Howlett and Ramesh 2014).

- In Italy, the Emergency Technical–Scientific Committee was facing challenges in possessing the relevant resources in managing guidelines for returning students to class following the peak of the first wave of COVID-19. One avenue was through improving the available infrastructure in schools through new school desks enabling flexible classroom arrangements. The Office of the Extraordinary Commissioner for the Covid Emergency utilised procurements through public-private initiatives for improving available resources. In the process, they utilised both hierarchy and market to create the venues, where actors are incentivised to contribute..
- With the increased turbulence from the refugee crisis in Spain, public sector organisations looked towards private and societal actors to complement limitations in addressing increased influx. This led to scaling up of existing civil society organisations (i.e. Asociación Comisión Católica Española de Migración, Red Cross) by subsidising their

activities. This enabled the societal actors to adopt a more comprehensive role in support services, such as education, healthcare, and employment assistance, which enabled to meet the demands from increased influx of refugees.

- During the financial crises, several countries also experienced the need to reconfigure existing incentive systems, with hierarchy and market configuration providing an option to respond to the heightened turbulence. In the case of Denmark, the central government implemented several Bank Packages in an effort to redesign the incentive system to ensure that banks were willing to collectively coordinate and take responsibility by having in place incentives that enabled collective actions. The bank packages included a variety of measures, from bailouts to guarantees of liabilities during takeovers to establish further stability in the financial system.

However, hierarchy and market-based tools may fixate on creating negotiation incentives, causing the goals to become misunderstood and ignoring key aspects of the problem. (Wu et al., 2015).

- The required requirements to resources and production during the COVID-19 crisis response in Italy was evaluated by a number of actors – Emergency Technical–Scientific Committee, Italian Ministry of Education, Extraordinary Commissioner for the Covid Emergency and the private companies. Whilst the initiative to procure further school desks highlighted the flexibility in activating additional resources, these resources had a limited impact due to a lack of interest by the recipients (schools). The lack of required assessment and interactions between actors resulted in misinterpreting the perceived need for the approach.
- In the case of Denmark, the refugee crisis indicated the challenges from flawed incentive systems. Denmark opted to adopt a set of policy measures (i.e. Asylum package, Rwanda solution, increased return capacity) oriented towards indirect deterrence. The aim was to reduce pressure on the refugee reception system, yet the hierarchy and market incentives created strong contestations with the legitimacy of the configuration.
- During the financial crisis, some countries also experienced challenges in framing goals and approaches. In the case of Estonia, the crisis response was aligned towards established political priorities in joining the Eurozone and adhering to the Maastricht treaty (public deficit under 3% of the GDP and government debt under 60%). This resulted in a hierarchy and market combination of strict austerity measures and cutback, which left public actors under pressure to meet increasing demand in the context of diminishing resources. Whilst the stakeholders utilised various means to meet the challenges, it also impacted the available slack and redundancies for future crisis responses.

With the use of hierarchy and market hybrid configurations, empirical illustrations on the EU level also reflected both synergies and dysfunctions. Synergies were reflected in the adoption of strategies to redesign existing incentive systems to be more viable to handle the heightened turbulence present during COVID-19. This was clearly reflected in the EU level initiative towards the vaccine procurements. During the first peak wave, the pre-existing mechanisms in the joint procurement schemes experienced failures, which resulted in coordination challenges at the supranational level. Some member states opted towards bilateral negotiations with manufacturers and established export bans for Personal Protective Equipment to ensure the availability of relevant infrastructure. As a response, the Commission adopted a hierarchical approach in centralising the interactions on behalf of member states with manufacturers through the Advance

Purchase Agreements. In June 2020, the Commission outlined a vaccine strategy and signed an agreement with each of the 27 MS, including the IVA countries, and 10 neighbouring states, which created a shift towards centralisation in the procurement process. Furthermore, through the Advance Purchase Agreements, the Commission also created an incentive system to steer the behaviour of manufacturers to create the necessary adaptability and security for production.

For vaccine procurement, certain dysfunctions also appeared with the use of hierarchy and market hybrids. During the first peak wave the joint procurement agreements (JPA) in use were based on previous pandemics (notably the 2009 H1N1 influenza outbreak). Through the Decision 1082/2013/EU, the JPA provided a framework for joint procurement procedures for medical countermeasures and outlined processes for joint procurement. However, the framework itself was adapted towards pandemics with a differing level of turbulence compared to COVID-19, creating tensions amongst MS. This resulted in insufficient flexibility and capacities with the deficiencies initially feeding into dysfunctions on the behalf of the member states. This led to the initial breakdown of the governance measures, as member states engaged in strategic behaviour and improving individual positions. This included improving available resources through measures like export bans on personal protective equipment (PPE). This led to interests of individual MS being prioritised over a collective response at the supranational level.

Limited and fixed perspectives can hamper legitimacy from related stakeholders (Ansell et al., 2022). The needs of the actors (local, regional and national) and their knowledge is crucial for reaching intended outcomes. The combinations between markets and hierarchies provide hybrids with significant modularity – from the activation of new resources to engagement of alternative perspectives to establishing more suitable goals and conditions towards nudging. These factors enable the configuration to create relevant conditions for *ad hoc* improvisations and readjustments to external signals. Through the readjustments, the crisis response structures engage new resources, which creates a new crisis response environment for both policy-making and implementation.

3.2.3. Market and network hybrid

Alongside the use of control, the incentives designed in the process of policymaking and implementation can also develop due to the shifts in the cost-benefit analyses and underlying motivation. This can lead to new **dynamics between markets and networks**. In crisis settings, the established coordinating logics can deviate, as actors are motivated to contribute beyond the goals and incentives previously established (Eckhard et al., 2021). This relates to the shared responsibility that actors adopt during moments of heightened turbulence that alter the consideration for stakeholders during the decision-making process.

- In the case of Estonia, during the early stages of the pandemic, existing clusters of private developers united in an effort to conduct hackathons in fostering new ideas to co-create through the pandemic. The most prominent example was through a cooperation initiated by Garage48 (a private company oriented towards fostering and supporting new start-ups, co-founded by several big Estonian tech companies) together with a number of private companies to devise potential solutions for tackling the crisis. In an effort to further foster the *ad hoc* initiatives, the public sector also provided support towards these hackathons to incentivise the brainstorming of new ideas.

- The creativity and ability to expand upon initial approaches was also highlighted in countries during the refugee crisis. In the case of Estonia, the limited resource available for the public actors (i.e. AS Hoolekandeteenused, Social Insurance Board, who are both responsible for providing services regarding reception and integration), resulted in the NGO's obtaining a larger role in providing for the necessary services. As they managed to adopt a larger role, the deliberations between public and societal actors led towards redesigns of the incentive system to accommodate for the heightened turbulence of refugees with higher influx and complementing this through further services, procured through private partners (i.e. translation, housing).
- During the financial crisis, societal actors organised to alleviate the heightened turbulence for citizens. For example, in Italy, the Italian Caritas, a Catholic non-profit organisation, established venues to provide a number of key services and access to needs (solidarity shopping, micro-credit initiatives, job orienteering, expansion of reception facilities, and strengthening of psychological listening centres). This was achieved through interactive venues engaging network associations and citizens' committee to determine the needs of the local community and tailoring the service provision accordingly.

However, their combinations can also create unexpected challenges due to the unexpectedness of the altered decision-making rationale. The inability of actors engaged within the cross-organisational venues to comprehend this momentum may result in the governance structures lacking the flexibility to adapt to the new conditions (Boersma et al., 2019).

- In Norway, some of the municipalities opted to consolidate key competencies and functions into municipal covid centres. Whilst this provided an opportunity to create synergies between the different actors and functions, it also created a demand for available resources. A key tool to mitigate this was through the use of volunteers. Some volunteer organisations were also contracted to conduct tasks. However, the use of financial compensation limited the flexibility of shifting roles and tasks for volunteers, as the bartering fixed specific actions and goals that had to be met. This highlights the challenges in combining the flexibility from network-based volunteerism principles with the clarity from market-based procurement.
- In the case of Spain, the challenges in fostering this dynamic were exhibited, as the civil society organisations (Asociación Comisión Católica Española de Migración, CEAR and the Red Cross) attempted to expand their activities following the establishment of the new incentive system by the regional and local governments. The reshifting roles of civil society organisations overstretched actors, who had to develop the necessary capacities to provide key services.

On the supranational level, actors (involving both the supranational institutions like the EU Commission, the European Council and the individual MS) are also engaged in the process of looking for potential opportunities through market and network hybrids. With regards to synergies, EU level cases highlighted an opportunity for more customisation and broader availability of perspectives. This was highlighted in the instance of the Recovery and Resilience Facility, where a more collaborative approach was looked for instead of a traditional top-down response. This included increased ownership for the member states with incentive framework established bottom-up through the national recovery and resilience plans (NRRP). Rather than prescribing the suitable steps, the member states were allowed to choose targets as long as the resources were in line with EU priorities. The interactions occurred through established venues

and included trilogues (i.e. the Ordinary Legislative Procedure), which included a broader set of stakeholders in the decision-making process. The blend created a venue for brokerage and fast-tracking legislation, essential for navigating the complexities of the crisis.

Whilst the market and network hybrid didn't exhibit clear dysfunctions, there were certain potential challenges present. The newly formed venues lacked similar rules and procedures for maintaining legitimacy. The bottom-up approach for the Recovery and Resiliency Facility and its urgency resulted in previously established monitoring capacities being insufficient for tracking the fair use of funds. This created additional burden for the member states to be more scrutinising with the use of funds made available through the Recovery and Resilience Facility.

The mixing between market and networks provides the hybrids with opportunities to foster creativity and innovation – from engaging in broader perspectives to reshaping existing processes and venues to catalysing from increased motivation. These factors provide the configuration for the creativity necessary in the improvisation process and ability to consider beyond already established alternatives. Through the readjustments, the crisis response structures engage new actors (and through this new resources), which enables further alternatives for crisis responses.

The functioning of hybrids is affected through the synergies and dysfunctions present in the mixes between tools and measures from different ideal types. The process of problem definition, alternative formulation, decision-making is affected through the underlying combination of logics and their balance. This also affects the orientation between the relative short-term and long-term nature of the configuration, as hybrids can exhaust existing resources, affecting the viability of a single option, and develop new resources, thus creating new options for future turbulent situations. Whilst during peak moments activation of resources in temporary coordination structures are necessary to alleviate the pressures towards the administrative systems, vicious cycles within administrative structures – whether due to the obfuscated roles in hierarchy and networks, orientation on wrong problems in hierarchy and market or the inability to redesign system goals in time from market and networks – may result in losing out on valuable potentialities for long-term shifts. This also can hamper long-term viability of hybrids, leading to potential reconfigurations. From the hybridity perspective, the multiplicity of options is important, as each combination provides different options for providing an acceptable solution. This includes strategies for short-term crisis responses as well as long-term options for heightened turbulence. The hybrids themselves occur in different forms at different levels, from local to national to supranational with each level providing options regarding the venues, the actors and the processes. Different governance hybrids enable to provide public administrations with different capacities to react to crises, as they shift from peak to off-peak moments. Through the ability of administrative structures to adjust to the conditions and shift from one governance hybrid to another, administrative structures become more able to robustly respond to the modern poly-crisis setting.

4. The inherently hybrid nature of robustness

In the current context marked by turbulence and polycrises, some argue that resilience, on the one hand, or agility, on the other, alone may not suffice to uphold societal goals and values (Ansell et al., 2022). In other words, stable and resilient organizations and policies are not enough

to respond to continuous disruption, but overly agile administrations may leave behind the core values and goals that are crucial for the maintenance of core functions of the public administration. Instead, there's a growing emphasis on robustness as an alternative governance paradigm, a perspective that attempts to readdress the existing relationship between stability and agility. Ansell and Trondal (2018) distinguish robustness from resilience by highlighting its focus on building flexibility into organizational and institutional structures. This flexibility enables adaptability to complexity, enhancing an organization's ability to navigate its evolving environment by incorporating variety and maintaining multiple repertoires that can be flexibly redeployed to meet changing circumstances (Ansell et al., 2022). Therefore, the appeal of robustness lies in its recognition that amidst turbulence, certain aspects of a system, institution, organization, or individual must adapt while others retain stability (Ansell et al., 2015). This also readdresses the relationship between stability and change, positing them not as mutually excluding features, but rather as mutually reinforcing characteristics necessary for administrative systems to operate in ever-changing conditions.

This contention underscores the inherently hybrid nature of robustness, as it involves blending stability and change to deliver effective responses. During a crisis, the normal process of deliberation and negotiation is hampered and shifts within the decision-making process are required, adopting varying coordination logics to make use of limited resources within a context of heightened turbulence. This is manifested in both the processes of policy making and implementation. Different tools and instruments, available and acceptable for actors, have to be ready for consistent shifts to meet the fluctuating turbulence. This can include a number of elements organisationally and cross-organisationally - division/consolidation of authority (centralized, decentralized), the position of a coordinating body (from single to delegated to shared coordination), civil society involvement (Meuleman 2008; Provan and Kenis 2008; Bovaird 2007; Verhoest et al. 2023), the allocation of resources available (financial, human and process resources - independent and interdependent resources) (Bovaird, Loeffler 2012; Kuipers et al., 2022), implementation processes (Boin and Lodge 2016; Meuleman 2008; Hooge et al., 2022). These elements and their constant shifts form parts of the crisis response structures, with the hierarchy-market-network trichotomy establishing the guiding underlying logic regarding their implementation. The dynamics between hybridity and robustness strategies are represented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Linkage between hybridity and robustness strategies

In practice, robustness is fostered through the different robustness strategies. They enable the administrative structures to adapt and react to the ongoing uncertainties provoked by the crisis and the subsequent shifts in priorities. The robustness strategies provide public administrations the necessary levers to adjust crucial structures, processes, and resources to maintain key functions and adapt to turbulent conditions. Robustness strategies necessitate re-interpretations and adjustments, which imply linkages with hybridity. The governance hybrids become linked to robustness strategies, as they provide public administrations with different enabling and impeding factors towards enacting the robustness strategies. Hybridity formation and its different combinations can be conducive for distinct robustness strategies, which rely on specific capacities to foster robustness. These capacities are fostered through governance hybrids, where the synergistic dynamics present in different hybrid configurations are utilised for the activation of different robustness strategies. Similarly, negative dysfunctions can impede the activation of robustness strategies, as the tensions and conflicts from the hybrids limit the ability to adjust critical structures, processes and resources. Therefore, the report posits that specific hybrid configurations with positive synergistic dynamics are conducive to distinct robustness strategies. This is highlighted in the empirical illustrations studied for the report, which illuminate the role of different governance hybrids in constructing the necessary capacities for different robustness strategies. Each governance hybrid tends to foster different robustness strategies, which attempt to create the necessary dynamic conservatism inherent to robustness. The linkages between hybrid governance configurations and robustness strategies are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Linkages between hybrid configurations and robustness strategies

Hybrid governance configuration	Conducive robustness strategies	Examples of robustness through hybridity
Hierarchy and network	Flexible adaptation	Self-governing crisis unit at the Nord-Funen Municipality adopting a contingency-

		based decision-making process
	Vigilance	Local decision-making venues in education policy of the City of Utrecht including other actors <i>ad hoc</i> to improve understanding on the problems and options
Hierarchy and market	Modularity and bricolage	Municipal Covid Center in Norway shifting personnel between different functions of the service by scaling down and up as required
	Redundancy, slack and buffering ¹	Emergency Science Technical Committee in Italy building competencies through engaging private partners
Market and network	Proactive real-time innovation	Clusters of private actors gathering for solve the crisis hackathons (i.e. Garage48 in Estonia)
	Multivocality and ambidexterity	Providing the children in Belgium digital equipment through societal actors, like the Digital for Youth and through donations from private companies

The linkages between the governance hybrids and robustness strategies were based on the existing theoretical knowledge and the findings from the country reports. Prior work within the ROBUST project on robustness strategies in D2.2 and existing academic work (i.e. Ansell et al., 2022) highlight that actors are constrained in their choices of robustness strategies due to a number of factors – i.e. organisational level determinants in organisational preferences, available resources and analytical abilities; system level determinants from existing legislative framework and past reform experiences; external factors in pressures from citizens and from the underlying crisis. These factors are also affected through governance hybrids, where the positive synergies and negative dysfunctions can constrain or enable actors with their choices. Alongside theory, the empirical illustrations also provided input on the linkages between different governance hybrids and robustness strategies.

#1 Strategy: Flexible adaptation

Flexibility and adaptability in managing complex systems in turbulent and unpredictable environments are at the core of robustness. In the face of uncertainty, flexibility and adaptability may come in many ways: in the human resources that possess the specialized skills and are ready to be mobilized (Roe and Schulman 2008); in the design of less rigid public policies (Capano and

¹ Redundancy, slack and buffering as a robustness strategy occurred also with other governance hybrids but it was highlighted most prominently through hierarchy and market governance hybrids.

Ramesh 2018), in the establishment of 'rules of exception' that allow standard operating procedures to be revised during exceptional events (LaPorte 2007: 62). Nevertheless, while flexibility is key, many authors posit that it thrives in well-established organizational contexts, that can combine "creative culture" (agility) with a "well-structured, well-defined process" (discipline) (Harrald 2006: 268, but also McCann, Selsky, and Lee 2009). In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, Moon (2020) attributes South Korea's effective response to their "agility-adaptability." Hence, our hypothesis is that hierarchy and network configurations primarily foster flexible adaptation. Hierarchy and network configurations facilitate flexibility by allowing decision-makers and organizations to maintain previously well-established structures, frequently hierarchical, while simultaneously setting up ad hoc networks, which gather skills and resources that the existing structures may not possess to achieve goals of and respond adequately to the different and ever-evolving challenges of a given crisis. In other words, the positive synergies between hierarchy and networks nurture the required flexibility and agility through the ability to include and activate stakeholders and shift existing roles and processes, which can provide public administrations the capacity to respond to the various challenges. This was also highlighted in the case of the Nord-Funen Municipality, where the contingency-based decisions provided flexibility to respond to different challenges whilst adhering to top-down guidelines.

#2 Strategy: Vigilance

As turbulence rises, public administrations also have to be able to recognise the increasing pressure and possess the ability to activate relevant response processes and structures. The challenges arise with the ability to detect heightened turbulence on time, as the complexity and uncertainty results in challenges in being able to evaluate the challenges and design a response. By being vigilant and establishing necessary feedback loops through the inclusion of broader perspectives are public administrations able to analyse pressures towards the existing administrative system on time and offer more alternatives, alleviating pressure as well as increasing the options for alternative solutions (Larruina et al., 2019). We hypothesise that a hierarchy and network hybrids contribute to vigilance. The formalisation and empowerment of a broad range of stakeholders can establish the basis for a more comprehensive monitoring and warning system, where different perspectives provide insight towards the underlying pressures, which establish the options for maintaining more vigilance. For the Municipal Covid Center in Norway, the available resources enabled to re-shift personnel to empower actors to conduct new processes for monitoring COVID-19.

#3 Strategy: Modularity and bricolage

A key element in managing the fluctuating levels of turbulence is through the recombination, reuse and repurposing of available governance tools and instruments. This is established through an increasing modular approach in the creating of new systems. Modularity enables "heterogeneous inputs to be recombined into a variety of heterogeneous configurations" (Schilling 2000: 315), namely the mix and matching of different instruments and skills (Law et al. 2012; Capano and Woo 2018). We posit that, particularly at the phase of implementation, the mixing and matching enabled through a hierarchy and market configuration is conducive towards the modularity and bricolage. Hierarchy and market configurations foster further modularity and bricolage by redesigning the incentives and goals of existing administrative systems to facilitate autonomy for improvisations amongst stakeholders. The positive synergies between hierarchy and markets provide the necessary urgency in redesigning the incentives in a timely manner yet maintaining autonomy in repurposing available tools and instruments and attracting new

perspectives. In the case of City of Utrecht's education policy, actors were provided the autonomy to include other actors for better quality decisions.

#4 Strategy: Redundancy, slack and buffering

During times of heightened turbulence, public administrations are under pressure to maintain core functions, which need further resource input due to increased demand. In the face of increasing demand, one option for public administrations is to make use of built-in slack. Providing certain redundancies and buffers within existing structures and processes, as well as the ability to activate available resources provides administrative systems long-term adaptiveness, enabling them to better react to unexpected challenges and threats (Howlett et al., 2018). We hypothesise that hierarchy and market hybrids are conducive towards redundancy, slack and buffering. The combination of hierarchy and market logic enables actors to design and enforce new incentive systems alongside options for engaging new resources. This can occur through slack within public sector organisations, but also with arrangements with private and societal actors. In the case of Emergency Science Technical Committee in Italy, the rapid redesign of the conditions for procurement enabled to engage further resources.

#5 Strategy: Proactive real-time innovation

Dealing with the uncertain and the unexpected often requires innovation, improvisation, and challenging dominant interpretations, particularly when "the rules are vague or incomplete" or where "the official tools provided by the plans are not available" Capano and Toth (2022:7). This creativity and innovation in the moment, created by the unfolding of the crisis, is enhanced by a framework which grants discretion to responsible actors but also facilitates coordination among them (Ansell et al., 2022). We therefore hypothesise that market and network configurations foster proactive real-time innovation. Market and network configurations can capture the difficult balance between establishing a level of coherence and coordination yet empower the different actors to innovate. This is established through positive synergies that provide an established frame through goals and incentives to maintain coherence yet encourage broad perspectives and interpretations regarding potential tools and instruments. In the case of Estonia, private developers were motivated through solidarity to come together and offer the new options for combatting COVID-19 (i.e. Garage48), which was supported by public sector organisations through funding.

#6 Strategy: Multivocality and ambidexterity

Modern crises entail significant complexity, which result in transboundary challenges, as stakeholders possess different perspectives to address the different pressures experienced (Ansell et al., 2010). One of the approaches available for public managers to coordinate within transboundary issues is through multivocality and ambidexterity. Through multivocality and ambidexterity, actors have established joint understanding in underlying goals, yet maintain flexibility in choosing the relevant evaluative criteria in the diverse contexts (Ferraro et al., 2015). We hypothesise that market and network configurations contribute towards multivocality and ambidexterity. This is established through a balance in logics that create a shared sense of understanding in joint goals yet maintain autonomy in devising differing evaluative criteria with independent actors operating within the shifting frames. In the case of Belgium, different platforms (i.e. Digital for Youth) and initiatives (i.e. donations from private companies) came together to provide children the necessary digital equipment to provide the necessary infrastructure to follow the guidelines.

In essence, robust governance operates on hybridity, leveraging the synergies between different ideal types to establish stability and innovation to navigate turbulent environments effectively. The forming and reforming of hybrids is conducive towards different robustness strategies that public administrations are then able to utilise. This is due to the capacities that the different hybrid configurations nurture within public administrations, which become the building blocks for the enactment of the robustness strategies. These capacities – from sharing situational awareness regarding detection, analysis and decision-making, to scaling up and fast-tracking necessary activities to managing trans-boundary structures – are established through the positive-sum synergies within hybrids. Positive-sum synergies occur, as the choice of policy tools and measures for administrative structures not merely co-exist, but interact and combine with each other in an effort to leverage the advantages and disadvantages of individual measures. As each hybrid instils different approaches towards enacting robustness strategies, administrative structures also have to be able to reconfigure, which furthers overall robustness. Maintaining openness towards reconfigurations provide public administrations the ability to shift from one hybrid configuration to another, in moments of tension maintaining core functions and in moments of opportunity, seeking improvement. Therefore, it is necessary to move away from the trends in literature regarding the use of hybrids as denoting broad generalisations and rather looking at hybrids as the frequent shifts that occur in the use of different modes of governance through introducing, reinterpreting and phasing out coordinating tools and measures.

The ability to opt towards reconfiguration and manage synergies and dysfunctions within established hybrids (as highlighted in Figure 5) is very complex, as it is impeded and enabled through different factors (covered through sections 3.1 and 3.2). As a result, administrative structures can have limited options for policy tools and measures available, which can lead to suboptimal hybrids that experience both internal (tension between policy measures) and external (tension between policy measures and problem environment) conflict. Over time the suboptimal hybrids are substituted, as the underlying tensions and conflicts reach a breaking point, leading to reconfiguration of hybrids. As actors receive feedback and learn from the dynamics between different policy measures, the administrative structures become more open towards new alternatives thus transitioning from dysfunctional dynamics. Through this, the hybrid consistently reconfigures from one state to another, whilst still managing both internal and external conflicts. In parallel, the hybrid configuration still develops capacities through positive-sum synergies present with other tools and measures implemented. This can result in hybrid configurations that may still provide the necessary capacities for enacting robustness strategies, but also experience internal and external conflicts.

Conclusion

This report has discussed how crises prompt actors to be innovative in meeting pressures, by adopting hybrid configurations. Although turbulence fosters creativity and the search for optimal solutions, crises result in a shift in the conditions for policymaking and implementation – through uncertainty, urgency, and pressure – that create a need for adaptations within public administrations. The existing literature provides several perspectives, but there remains a considerable emphasis on static perspectives that are more oriented towards stable environments. Hybridity provides a dynamic perspective towards the decision-making and implementation of public administrations regarding the tools and instruments available for them in the moments of heightened turbulence. The ability to flexibly adapt to new conditions yet

maintain the core functions is conducive towards establishing robustness of public administrations.

Hybridity is an important factor in the ability of public administrations to foster robustness. This is established through its contributions in alternative selection and dynamics within formed hybrids. Once new hybrid configurations are established, they undergo dynamics that influence their viability and the necessity for reconfiguration. This cycle forms the basis for robustness. The combination of different ideal-type tools and measures can create positive-sum dynamics by supplementing and complementing each other, even if challenges arise from factors such as resource scarcity, strategic interests, or lack of trust. However, tensions between different tools and measures within hybrids can lead to deviations from initial goals and, in severe cases, render the hybrid unviable. The compatibility and conflicts between various ideal type approaches play a crucial role in fostering viability and enabling adjustments or reconfigurations when necessary. Combining hierarchy and networks in crisis management, for example, can provide speed and clarity alongside inclusiveness and legitimacy, but clarity in roles and long-term sustainability may be compromised. Similarly, incentives and rational behaviour logic become crucial in crisis contexts, facilitating exchanges of resources and their reinterpretations, but misaligned goals or lack of local perspectives can hinder effectiveness. The mix of markets and networks offers flexibility and innovation but may also pose challenges in decision-making and resource allocation.

Hybrid governance, integrating diverse tools and measures from multiple ideal types, can enhance crisis management robustness by leveraging complementary strengths and mitigating weaknesses. For instance, by combining hierarchy's command and control with networks' flexibility, hybrid approaches can foster flexible adaptation within public administrations through rapid response and broad stakeholder engagement during crises. This dynamic balance allows for timely decision-making while ensuring legitimacy and buy-in from various actors. The mixing between the incentives from market-based instruments and command and control from hierarchy can foster modularity and bricolage in existent systems. By rapidly reshaping the goals and incentives in existent systems, actors are provided the autonomy to interpret and reinterpret tools and instruments available for them. Moreover, the synergy between incentives from markets and solidarity from networks can mobilize resources effectively and foster pro-active real-time innovation. The consistent reforming enables hybrid governance to navigate the complexities of crises, adjusting towards different robustness strategies as needed and maintaining resilience in the face of evolving challenges. Overall, hybrid governance offers a comprehensive and dynamic framework that maximizes the utilization of available resources, fosters collaboration across sectors, and enhances the overall robustness of crisis management systems. However, if impediments and dysfunctions are not identified, avoided, or properly dealt with, hybridity may in fact undermine robustness in crisis management. Ultimately, the functioning of hybrids depends on the ability to form and reform configurations to nurture the capacities for different robustness strategies and thus address impediments regarding pressures and viability for both short-term crises and long-term turbulence.

References

- Ansell, C., Boin, A. & Farjoun, M. (2015) Dynamic conservatism: how institutions change to remain the same. *In: Kraatz, M.S. (Ed.) Institutions and ideals: Philip Selznick's legacy for organizational studies. Emerald: Bingley*, 89–119.
- Ansell, C., Sørensen, E. and Torfing, J. (2023). Public administration and politics meet turbulence: The search for robust governance responses. *Public Administration*, 101(1), 3-22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12874>
- Ansell, C., Sørensen, E. & Torfing, J. (2021) The COVID-19 pandemic as a game changer for public administration and leadership? The need for robust governance responses to turbulent problems. *Public Management Review*, 23(7), 949–960.
- Ansell C., Trondal J., (2018). Governing Turbulence: An Organizational- Institutional Agenda, *Perspectives on Public Management and Governance*, 1(1), 43–57, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ppmgov/gvx013>
- Baekkeskov, E. (2016). Explaining science-led policy-making: pandemic deaths, epistemic deliberation and ideational trajectories. *Policy Sciences* 49, 395–419 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-016-9264-y>
- Boersma, K, Kraiukhina, A, Larruina, R, Lehota, Z, Nury, EO. (2019) A port in a storm: Spontaneous volunteering and grassroots movements in Amsterdam. A resilient approach to the (European) refugee crisis. *Social Policy and Administration*, 53(5), 728–742. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spol.12407>
- Boin, A. & Bynander, F. (2015). Explaining Success and Failure in Crisis Coordination. *Geografiska Annaler: Series A, Physical Geography*, 97(1), 123-135.
- Boin, A., Lodge, M. (2016). Designing Resilient Institutions for Transboundary Crisis Management: a time for Public Administration. *Public Administration*, 94(2), 289-298. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12264>
- Boin, A., Lodge, M. (2021). Responding to the COVID-19 crisis: a principled or pragmatist approach?, *Journal of European Public Policy*, 28:8, 1131-1152, DOI:10.1080/13501763.2021.1942155
- Boin, A., McConnell, A. (2007). Preparing for Critical Infrastructure Breakdowns: The Limits of Crisis Management and the Need for Resilience. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 15(1), 50-59, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-5973.2007.00504.x>
- Boin, A., McConnell, A., 't Hart, P. (2020). Governing the Pandemic. The Politics of Navigating a Mega-Crisis. *Palgrave Pivot Cham*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-72680-5>
- Bouckaert, G., Peters, G. B., Verhoest, K. (2010). *The Coordination of Public Sector Organizations: Shifting Patterns of Public Management*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Bovaird, T. (2007). “Beyond Engagement and Participation: User and Community Coproduction of Public Services” *Public Administration Review*, Vol. 67, No. 5, 846-860.
- Bovaird, T., Loeffler, E. (2012). “From Engagement to Co-production: The Contribution of Users and Communities to Outcomes and Public Value.” *Voluntas*, Vol. 23, 1119–1138.
- Brandsen, T., & Karré, P. M. (2011). Hybrid organizations: No cause for concern? *International Journal of Public Administration*, 34(13), 827 - 836.
- Capano, G. & Toth, F. (2022). Thinking Outside the Box, Improvisation, and Fast Learning: Designing Policy Robustness to Deal with what Cannot be Foreseen. *Public Administration*, early view.
- Capano, G. & Woo, J. J. (2018). Designing Policy Robustness: Outputs and Processes. *Policy & Society*, 37(4), 422-440.

- Christensen, T., Lægreid, P. and Rykkja, L.H. (2016), Organizing for Crisis Management: Building Governance Capacity and Legitimacy. *Public Administration Review*, 76(6), 887-897. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12558>
- Cristofoli, D., Cucciniello, M., Micacchi, M., Trivellato, B., Turrini, A., & Valotti, G. (2022). One, none, and a hundred thousand recipes for a robust response to turbulence. *Public Administration*, 101(1), 106-123.
- Dryzek, J. S. (2009). Democratization as Deliberative Capacity Building. *Comparative Political Studies*, 42(11), 1379–1402. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0010414009332129>
- Eckhard, S., Lenz, A., Seibel, W., Roth, F., & Fatke, M. (2021). Latent Hybridity in Administrative Crisis Management: The German Refugee Crisis of 2015/16. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 31(2), 416-433.
- Hendriks, F. (2022). Key values for democratic governance innovation: Two traditions and a synthesis. *Public Administration*, 100, 803–820. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12738>
- Hermansson, H.M.L. (2016). Disaster Management Collaboration in Turkey: Assessing Progress and Challenges of Hybrid Network Governance. *Public Administration*, 94(2), 333-349. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12203>
- Hooge, E. H., Waslander, S., Theisens, H. C. (2022). The many shapes and sizes of meta-governance. An empirical study of strategies applied by a well-advanced meta-governor: the case of Dutch central government in education. *Public Management Review*, 24(10), 1591-1609, DOI: 10.1080/14719037.2021.1916063
- Howlett, M., Ramesh, M. (2014). The two orders of governance failure: Design mismatches and policy capacity issues in modern governance. *Policy and Society*, 33(4), 317–327.
- Howlett, M. (2019) Procedural policy tools and the temporal dimensions of policy design. *International Review of Public Policy*, 1(1), 27–45.
- Jessop, B. (2003). Governance and Metagovernance: On Reflexivity, Requisite Variety, and Requisite Irony. In: *Governance, as Social and Political Communication*. Manchester University Press, Manchester, 142-172.
- Jugl, M. (2023). Administrative characteristics and timing of governments' crisis responses: A global study of early reactions to COVID-19. *Public Administration*, 101(4), 1408–1426. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12889>
- Koppenjan, J., Karré, P. M., & Termeer, C. J. A. M. (Eds.) (2019). *Smart Hybridity. Potentials and Challenges of New Governance Arrangements*. Eleven International Publishing.
- Kuipers, S., van der Wilt, A. and Wolbers, J. (2022). Pandemic publishing: A bibliometric review of COVID-19 research in the crisis and disaster literature. *Risks, Hazards & Crisis in Public Policy*, 13, 302-321. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rhc3.12262>
- Law, E. A., Thomas, S., Meijaard, E., Dargusch, P. J., & Wilson, K. A. (2012). A Modular Framework for Management of Complexity in International Forest-Carbon Policy. *Nature Climate Change*, 2(3), 155-160.
- Lee S., Wong R. (2021). COVID-19 Responses of South Korea as Hybrids of Governance Modes. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, DOI=10.3389/fpubh.2021.654945
- Levi-Faur, D. (2014). The Welfare State: A Regulatory Perspective. *Public Administration*, 92(3), 599-614. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12063>
- Meuleman, L. (2008). Public Management and the Metagovernance of Hierarchies, Networks and Markets. *Physica Heidelberg*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-7908-2054-6>
- Meuleman, L. (2019). *Metagovernance for Sustainability. A Framework for Implementing the Sustainable Development Goals*. Routledge.

- Moon, M. J. (2020). Fighting COVID-19 with Agility, Transparency, and Participation: Wicked Policy Problems and New Governance Challenges. *Public Administration Review*, 80(4), 651-656.
- Moynihan, D. (2020). "Populism and the deep state: the attack on public service under Trump." SSRN. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3607309>
- Moynihan, D. P. (2008). Learning Under Uncertainty: Networks in Crisis Management. *Public Administration Review*, 68(2), 350-365.
- Nohrstedt, D. Bynander, F., Parker, C., 't Hart, P. (2018). Managing Crises Collaboratively: Prospects and Problems—A Systematic Literature Review. *Perspectives on Public Management and Governance*, 1(4), 257–271.
- O'Flynn, J. (2021). Confronting the big challenges of our time: making a difference during and after COVID-19, *Public Management Review*, 23(7), 961-980.
- Pollitt, C., Bouckaert, G. (2011). *Public Management Reform: A Comparative Analysis – New Public Management, Governance, and the Neo-Weberian State*. (3rd ed.) Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Provan, K. G., Kenis. P. (2008). "Modes of Network Governance: Structure, Management, and Effectiveness." *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, Vol. 18, No.2 229–252.
- Schilling, M. A. (2000). Toward a General Modular Systems Theory and Its Application to Inter-firm Product Modularity. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(2), 312-334.
- Skelcher, C., Smith, S. R. (2015). Theorizing Hybridity: Institutional Logics, Complex Organisations and Actor Identities: The Case of Nonprofits. *Public Administration*, 93(2), 433-448.
- Sørensen, E. and Torfing, J. (2019), Towards Robust Hybrid Democracy in Scandinavian Municipalities? *Scandinavian Political Studies*, 42, 25-49. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9477.12134>
- Tenbenschel, T. (2018). Bridging complexity theory and hierarchies, markets, networks, communities: a 'population genetics' framework for understanding institutional change from within. *Public Management Review*, 20(7), 1032-1051, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2017.1364409>
- Teubner, G. (1983). Substantive and Reflexive Elements in Modern Law. *Law & Society Review* 17(2), 239–86.
- Vecchiato, R. (2015). Strategic Planning and Organizational Flexibility in Turbulent Environments. *Foresight*, 17(3), 257-273.
- Verhoest K., Callens, C., Klijn, E. H., Brogaard, L., García-Rayado, J., and Nömmik, S. (2023). Designing Cross-Sector Collaboration to Foster Technological Innovation: Empirical Insights from eHealth Partnerships in Five Countries. *Public Administration Review* 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.13785>
- Warren, M. (2017). A Problem-Based Approach to Democratic Theory. *American Political Science Review*, 111(1), 39-53. doi:10.1017/S0003055416000605
- Wolbers, J., Ferguson, J., Groenewegen, P., Mulder, F., & Boersma, K. (2016). Two Faces of Disaster Response: Transcending the Dichotomy of Control and Collaboration during the Nepal Earthquake Relief Operation. *International Journal of Mass Emergencies & Disasters*, 34(3), 419–438.
- Wu X., Ramesh M. & M. Howlett (2015) Policy capacity: A conceptual framework for understanding policy competences and capabilities, *Policy and Society*, 34(3-4), 165-171, DOI: 10.1016/j.polsoc.2015.09.001

Zeitlin J., Nicoli F. & Laffan B. (2019). Introduction: the European Union beyond the polycrisis? Integration and politicization in an age of shifting cleavages, *Journal of European Public Policy*, 26(7), 963-976, DOI: 10.1080/13501763.2019.1619803